

Missed the Moment? Opportunity Windows and Digital Agenda in BRICS+

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Abstract

This paper examines the evolution of the digital governance agenda within the BRICS+ grouping, focusing on whether member states have been able to align their policy responses to perceived challenges in the current global digital order. The study argues that growing concerns over data sovereignty and technological dependence, brought to light by the Snowden case in 2013 and the Tech War in 2019, have stimulated demands for regulatory reform and enhanced state control over digital infrastructures. Using Kingdon's Multiple Streams Framework, the paper analyses the period from 2014 to 2025, drawing on official BRICS+ documents and academic literature. The findings suggest that, although policy ideas and problem recognition have advanced, political convergence among member states remains limited, slowing the institutionalization of deeper cooperation and rule-making initiatives in the digital domain.

Keywords: BRICS; Technology; Agenda Coupling.

Introduction

Debates surrounding digital governance have increased exponentially in recent years, particularly given the growing relevance of this issue in light of the expanding influence of large technology companies and their access to sensitive societal data. This close interaction with both citizens' data and critical state infrastructures raises important concerns related to national sovereignty and cybersecurity. The current configuration of global digital governance can be understood, to a significant extent, as a system that tends to reinforce the hegemonic position of the United States and its major technology corporations, granting them considerable capacity for surveillance and structural influence over other countries in the international system.

In this context, an emerging international movement has called for reforms in the governance of digital technologies and the internet, advocating greater accountability, transparency, and, above all, enhanced state sovereignty in cyberspace within national borders. Countries such as China, often portrayed as a leading actor in this field and an important representative of the Global South, have been particularly vocal in promoting such changes. However, other states have also expressed similar demands or have sought to implement domestic regulatory initiatives independently, including Russia and India (Belli, 2025).

The BRICS+ grouping, as a relevant coalition of Global South countries with active participation in international debates on digital governance, has established several working groups, cooperative frameworks, and political declarations addressing technological issues. Although it does not constitute a formal international organization, BRICS+ provides a platform for agenda coordination and interest convergence among its members through cooperative initiatives, memoranda of understanding, diplomatic channels, and other flexible mechanisms. Consequently, the group possesses certain institutional tools to promote the articulation of shared interests and, to some extent, the development of common policy orientations, albeit with relatively limited levels of formal obligation.

Against this background, this paper aims to evaluate the process of agenda coupling within the BRICS+ digital agenda in order to assess whether it has evolved in response to the perceived need for changes in global digital governance over time. To achieve this objective, the study applies John Kingdon's Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) (2014), covering the period from 2014, marked by the emergence of the group's technological agenda, to 2025. The analysis draws on both primary sources produced within the BRICS+ framework and secondary academic literature in order to examine the development and institutionalization of this agenda. Ultimately, the paper seeks to contribute to the scholarly literature by offering a systematic assessment of the trajectory, scope, and limitations of BRICS+ cooperation in the technological and digital governance domain.

Agenda Coupling And International Regimes

This research utilizes the theoretical framework proposed by Kingdon (2014), known as the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF), to analyze the agenda coupling regarding the topic of digital cooperation, development and governance within BRICS+. It is worth noting that the MSF is an approach commonly associated and used for analyzing public policymaking processes, but it can be applied in analysis regarding international matters as well.

With that being said, the MSF identifies three processes, or streams, in policymaking: Problem, Policy, and Politics. Those streams are independent of each other and are constantly developing at the same time in the policymaking arena. The Problem Stream is defined on the identification and definition of issues as problems, which involves actors like the media and policy communities in public debate on how to frame and define a problem based on different perspectives. Meanwhile, the Policy Stream concerns itself with the development of potential policy solutions based on research, effectiveness, and resources needed. At last, the Politics Stream deals with the public opinion and political climate surrounding the issue, with policymakers considering their own political positions, public support, and impacts on their political stance. (Kingdon, 2014)

The policy change happens when all three of those streams converge during a policy window-opportunity, when it is most likely to accept changes. Those windows are opened either by the appearance of compelling problems or by happenings in the political streams. During these moments, policy entrepreneurs link recognized problems to available solutions, allowing certain issues to enter the decision-making agenda and increasing the likelihood that policy change will occur if the political climate is favorable. (Kingdon, 2014)

Regarding BRICS+, although it is not formally an international organization but rather a political discussion forum (BRICS Brasil, 2025), this paper considers that it possesses a sufficient degree of institutionalization to be analyzed through the MSF. Since the first three BRICS summits, which defined the characteristics that would shape the group throughout the years, the group has been an arrangement with a low-level institutionalization (Silva; Gomes, 2019). It is characterized by the lack of a constitutive agreement, secretariat or headquarters, but has established the Contingent Reserves Agreements (CRA), the New Development Bank (NDB), cooperation frameworks and yearly meetings - which have mechanisms that generate obligations (Silva; Gomes, 2019). Moreover, the group allows its members to establish common positions and cooperation in a diverse range of topics beyond the group itself in the international arena.

According to Krasner (1983, p.2), international regimes are “sets of principles, norms and implicit or explicit rules and decision-making procedures in a particular area of international relations around which the expectations of the actors converge.” In addition, regimes are not given structures, they are built upon common actions and do not require a formal institutionalization (Krasner, 1983). Thus, BRICS+ fulfills the criteria to be analyzed as a

channel for agenda coupling among its member countries in the international arena.

The Streams Of The BRICS+ Digital Agenda

To analyze the BRICS+ digital agenda, the MSF will be applied to a timeframe that begins in 2014, the year in which the first topics around technology began within BRICS, and ends with the current developments in 2025. The analysis will be organized in accordance with the structure of streams proposed by the MSF, with the agenda coupling processes explained in the next section.

Regarding the Problem Stream, the Snowden case brought the issue of digital sovereignty and technological independence to the forefront of international debate. In 2013, Edward Snowden disclosed a series of global surveillance programs conducted by the National Security Agency (NSA), revealing extensive intelligence operations targeting governments, institutions, and individuals worldwide. The revelations included evidence that the communications of several heads of state had been monitored, among them Dilma Rousseff of Brazil and Angela Merkel of Germany. (Pohle; Van Audenhove, 2017; Lyon, 2014)

According to Kurbalija (2016), these disclosures significantly intensified global concerns about digital sovereignty, data security, and the dependence of states on foreign technological infrastructures. The issue was subsequently raised by several countries in multilateral forums, particularly within the UN General Assembly and the UN Human Rights Council, where governments sought to debate the implications of mass surveillance for privacy, human rights, and international governance of digital technologies.

Since then, many countries have demanded clearer rules governing the data collection and surveillance practices of large technology companies. In this context, governments increasingly adopted concepts such as “internet sovereignty” or “digital sovereignty” implementing new regulatory frameworks and public policies within their national borders. With that being said, the idea of dependence on the existing U.S.-centric global digital order and the digital infrastructure of American companies became an issue.

In the case of the Policy Stream, the BRICS has several working groups and frameworks related to technology that have discussed recommendations related to the main problem above. This stream includes policy ideas circulating among experts, diplomats, and technical communities among BRICS. Post-Snowden, the 2015 BRICS Summit issued the Ufa Declaration to establish a working group on the security of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which intended to address common security concerns and share information on ICT policies (Beli, 2015). During the same year, BRICS launched the Moscow Declaration, where the STI ministers established working groups on research infrastructure and on funding multilateral joint research projects, as well as agreeing to implement the BRICS Framework Programme on multilateral research funding through joint calls (BRICS, 2015b).

Going further beyond, the Xiamen Declaration, issued after the 9th BRICS Summit in 2017, advocated for the establishment of internationally applicable rules for security of ICT infrastructure, data protection and the Internet (Belli, 2025). Furthermore, in 2021, the New Delhi Declaration explicitly called for the establishment of a legal framework of cooperation on critical issues, such as ICTs development and security (Jiang; Belli, 2025).

During the 11th BRICS Communications Ministers Meeting in 2025, in Brasilia, technology was addressed from the perspective of telecommunications infrastructure and space governance. Meeting under Brazil's chairship, the ministers focused on connectivity, space sustainability, environmental sustainability, and digital ecosystems. Moreover, artificial intelligence, quantum technologies, and innovation were also core themes discussed throughout the year in working groups on STI Funding, STI and Entrepreneurship Partnership (STIEP), and High-Performance Computing and Artificial Intelligence. (BRICS, 2025a; BRICS, 2025b; BRICS, 2025c)

On the Political Stream, the BRICS members, at least the core five until the expansion of 2024, have different positions, policies and interests regarding digital sovereignty. These differences are a main problem to the agenda coupling for the group. Thumfart (2025) argues that China, Russia and India have an authoritarian perception of digital sovereignty, which is related to cultural and security concerns. Although these three countries share similar interpretations of the concept, their positions are not entirely aligned with those of other members of the BRICS grouping. Differences in political systems, regulatory traditions, and approaches to internet governance generate tensions with countries such as Brazil and South Africa, which generally support more open and multistakeholder models of digital governance.

Thus, with the expansion of BRICS+ in 2024, the collective understanding of digital governance and digital sovereignty within the bloc became more complex. Although the group broadly shares an anti-hegemonic stance toward the technological dominance of the United States, many of the new members and partner countries bring diverse political, regulatory, and technological backgrounds, as well as differing positions on issues related to data governance, internet regulation, and state control over digital infrastructure.

Did the Streams Converge or We Missed the Moment?

As stated above, the Snowden case in 2013 changed the debate around digital privacy and sovereignty around the world. It can be argued that it was a policy window-opportunity for the BRICS countries to gather and propose between themselves or create a coalition as a group to defend their common interests regarding new rules and regulations for cyberspace. However, in 2014, during the the First BRICS Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Ministerial Meeting, held in Cape Town, the five countries defined five thematic areas and leadership for technological development and cooperation: climate change and natural disaster mitigation (Brazil), water resources and pollution treatment (Russia), geospatial

technology and its applications (India), new and renewable energy, energy efficiency (China), astronomy (South Africa). (BRICS, 2014).

Later, in March 2015, BRICS signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on Cooperation in Science, Technology and Innovation through the Brasília Declaration. In this MoU, the countries agreed to develop a work plan 2015-2018 focusing on the five priority areas established the previous year, demonstrating continuity and commitment to the distributed leadership model (BRICS, 2015a). Moreover, it cited a range of cooperation modalities, such as researcher exchanges, joint training programs, collaborative R&D projects, shared access to infrastructure, information exchange, and coordinated calls for proposals (BRICS, 2015a)

Even after the Ufa Declaration and the creation of numerous working groups to discuss the matter, between 2016 and 2017 the BRICS digital agenda was marked by the operationalization of joint research funding, beginning with the signing of the BRICS STI Framework Program Arrangement and the launch of the first Pilot Call for multilateral projects in 2016. Furthermore, in 2017, the Action Plan for Innovation Cooperation was adopted to promote entrepreneurship, technology transfer, and university-industry partnerships. (Kubota, 2019)

Continuing the trend of the previous years, the BRICS Partnership on New Industrial Revolution (PartNIR) was introduced by President Xi Jinping at the 10th BRICS Summit in 2018. The PartNIR is dedicated to cooperation in areas related to the New Industrial Revolution, digitalization, and technologies. It also encompasses six cooperation projects: 1. BRICS PartNIR Innovation Center (BPIC); 2. BRICS-UNIDO Center for Industrial Competences Initiative; 3. BRICS Startups Cooperation Initiative; 4. BRICS Technology Transfer Center; 5. BRICS Institute of Future Networks; and 6. Digital BRICS Task Force. With this development, the BRICS digital agenda continued to prioritize funding for projects, research, and cooperation aimed at incremental, technical-level innovation. (BPIC, 2026)

Another policy window-opportunity emerged with the beginning of the U.S. Tech War against China in 2019, during the first presidential term of Donald Trump. During this period, the U.S. administration began to politically and diplomatically target major Chinese technology companies and their devices, arguing that they posed national security risks. These measures extended beyond domestic restrictions, affecting the operations of Chinese technology firms in third countries and seeking to limit their commercialization and participation in telecommunications and digital infrastructure markets both in the United States and internationally. (Harold e Kamijima-Tsunoda, 2021; Danilin, 2022; Wong, 2022)

With that being said, the 12th BRICS STI Ministerial Meeting happened in 2024, after the BRICS+ expansion. This meeting limited itself to welcome the new member states (Egypt, Ethiopia, Iran, and the United Arab Emirates) in the BRICS STI Framework and launch specific flagship projects like the BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network (BITDN), and the BRICS GRAIN research infrastructure network. (BRICS, 2024)

In the same vein, in 2025, the 13th BRICS STI Ministerial Meeting released a declaration welcoming Indonesia as a new BRICS member and ten additional nations as partners (Belarus, Bolivia, Cuba, Kazakhstan, Malaysia, Nigeria, Thailand, Uganda, Uzbekistan, Vietnam). During the meeting the ministers approved an Accession Protocol to the STI MoU to formally incorporate the new members and set priorities related to artificial intelligence, quantum technologies, and innovation. (BRICS, 2025d)

It is worth noting that throughout the years, the BRICS+ has financed a number of projects and researches that revolve around ICT and digital infrastructure through its frameworks, PartNIR (BPIC, 2026) and the New Development Bank (NDB) - with the latter only having one project on this matter (NDB, 2026).

Thus the BRICS+ digital agenda remains largely focused on the development of institutional frameworks for funding of working groups, research projects, researcher exchanges, joint training programs and similar initiatives. Although political discussions in summit meetings and official declarations have urged for the construction of new rules and cooperation on digital governance, concrete mechanisms have progressed gradually and no institution of BRICS+ on the matter is to be seen on the horizon. Compared to other areas of cooperation, particularly the financial agenda with the creation of the NDB and other mechanisms, the digital agenda reflects the divergent national interests of its member states on the matter.

Conclusion

By evaluating the process of agenda coupling through the lens of the MSF, it was possible to clearly see that the member states have identified the persistence of a U.S.-centric global digital order as a central problem. Within this context, these countries perceive themselves as dependent on Western technological paradigms, digital infrastructures, and governance models. Furthermore, those countries also are exposed to potential external surveillance practices that may affect their sovereignty without any mechanism of accountability.

Consequently, this perceived asymmetry reinforces their strategic interest in promoting greater technological autonomy and enhancing regulatory influence in the international system. Based on this, there are ongoing ideas and demands within BRICS+ framework aimed at reshaping or counterbalancing the current digital order, particularly through the development of clearer norms and cooperation regarding data collection, governance and surveillance practices. These ideas are articulated in specialized working groups, multilateral joint projects, and official meetings involving experts and political authorities.

However, even with at least two policy window-opportunities identified by this paper - the Snowden case and the Tech War -, the BRICS+ digital agenda has not fully encompassed cooperation and binding rule-making initiatives that change the current digital order. Although both the Problem Stream and the Policy Stream showed signs of alignment during

these critical junctures, the Political Stream did not converge to the same extent. Based on the MSF, the absence of simultaneous convergence among all three streams limited the opening of a sustained policy change. The outcome can be explained by the different perspectives and goals of BRICS+ members regarding digital governance and technological development strategies, all of which have become even more pronounced following the group's expansion.

In summary, this paper has presented the BRICS+ digital agenda as a victim of the divergent interests and concepts of its member states around digital sovereignty and governance. With that, the agenda became limited to the development of institutional frameworks for funding of working groups, research projects, researcher exchanges, joint training programs and similar initiatives, instead of the creation of solid institutions on the matter, such as the NDB for the financial agenda.

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